

D5.1. Best Practices Report

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING ROLES tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
Task 5.1	Identify best practices
Task 5.2	Analysis of Leadership at each institution

GEARING-Roles Project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project, therefore, has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in these areas, mentoring activities and awareness-raising campaigns, as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
HEI	Higher Education Institution
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
UDEUSTO	University of Deusto
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This documents gathers a number of inspiring practices around the promotion of leadership in HEI. The aim of this desk analysis is to identify initiatives and programmes developed in HEI, but also in other fields to foster leadership, and especially, female leadership. This report is based on secondary resources but also on the answers provided to an online survey spread among the Euraxess community to map and assess current existing practices.

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1. Introduction

Despite notorious advancement in the actions for the advancement of women at work in European policies and legislation, putting these actions into practice often remains a challenge. The specific issue of advancing women in leadership and top managerial positions is particularly relevant, given women's limited progress in these levels (Eagly, Gartzia & Carli, 2012; Ely, Ibarra & Kolb, 2011). In general, female leaders encounter many disadvantages that flow from distrust about their abilities as leaders. The fundamental properties of this discrimination are captured in the notion of incongruity between the characteristics usually ascribed to women and the characteristics typically ascribed to leaders (Eagly & Karau, 2002; see also Burgess & Borgida, 1999; Heilman, 2001). People tend to think of women in association with stereotypically feminine, communal qualities such as being nice, warm, and friendly, whereas they typically think of leaders in association with stereotypically masculine, agentic qualities such as assertiveness, competitiveness, and ambition. This incongruity between the group stereotype about women and the requirements of leadership roles represents one of the strongest obstacles for women in leadership. Over decades, this phenomenon called the "think manager, think male" paradigm has been captured across different studies. The initial research by Schein (1973) has been widely replicated showing that participants view leaders as more in line with agentic traits and male-typed, especially in the minds of men (see meta-analytical review by Koenig, Eagly, Mitchell, and Ristikari, 2011).

These masculine images of leadership coupled with gender stereotypes and the stereotypical association of women with domestic roles create suspicion of women's leadership competences such that even female leaders with objectively good professional qualifications usually have to overcome concerns that they are not good enough to be in leadership positions. As a result, a double standard arises whereby female leaders have to be better qualified than their male counterparts for a managerial position (e.g., Lyness & Heilman, 2006). Furthermore, these gender stereotypes can also serve as a self-fulfilling prophecy making it less desirable for women to become leaders, as repeatedly shown in studies about the stereotype threat. For instance, these studies ask participants to choose a leader or subordinate role for an organizational task after viewing ads with gender stereotypical contents of women (vs. ads with non-stereotypical content). Results show that making salient the gender stereotype about women caused the women themselves to express less interest in becoming a leader and instead more interest in taking a subordinate role (Davies, Spencer, & Steele, 2005). In other words, socially shared gender stereotypes about women are preventing women themselves from becoming leaders. The fact that domestic functions are commonly taken by women is also harmful for women's leadership career by limiting their access to decision-making positions or generating the expectation that they are less committed to such leadership roles (Mandel & Semyonov, 2005; Gupta et al., 2006). These findings are often referred to as a "motherhood penalty/fatherhood bonus" (Hodges & Budig, 2010), capturing the idea that female employees with

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children have an additional disadvantage in their promotion to leadership roles compared to male employees (Hersch & Stratton, 2002).

To overcome these obstacles, many international norms and policies aimed at promoting women's development at work have been implemented. In Europe, relevant programs have been developed put into place to reduce gender stereotypes in the workplace that have translated into specific arrangements like affirmative action programs for the advancement of women in decision-making in public and private organizations (European Commission, 2015). Unfortunately, regular implementations of gender equality plans in the workplace tend to adopt an "add-women-and-stir" approach in which gender equality actions are delivered without a critical appraisal (Martin & Meyerson, 1998, p. 312). As a consequence, progress of women in improving their situation of discrimination in the workplace and in particular in promoting to leadership positions is very slow (United Nations, 2015). To move forward, it is necessary that organizations develop actions aimed at incorporating gender equality as a more distinctive and strategic feature. In relation to this, Grosser and Moon (2008) underscored the complementary roles of social/political actions and self-regulation of private companies becoming inherently more engaged and concerned with gender equality. Consistent with this idea, identifying best practices that are taking place in actual organizations and can serve to overcome these obstacles and foster gender equality is a relevant step.

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2. Identification of Best Practices

The practices gathered in this report are coming from two different sources. On the one hand, the desk research analysis performed by the team of the University of Deusto, aimed at identifying best practices across the world on female leadership and decision making. On the other hand, the WP5 team in close collaboration with FECYT has designed a survey to identify practices and initiatives among EURAXESS members. The aim of this twofold analysis was to Identify:

1. Consolidated practices with proven success on the promotion and fostering of female leadership in Research and Higher Education Institutions. This collection of experiences and information on the results achieved are expected to guide GEP implementing institutions on the design and implementation of actions to promote access of women to leadership positions.
2. Emerging practices and experiences of European Institutions engaged in the EURAXESS network in redefining organizational decision making structures from a gender perspective and developing equal representation of women in leadership positions in the field of research and higher education. The survey spread among the networks' members covering 42 countries - EU Member States and Associated Countries- a over 600 organizations, was a simple questionnaire structured in 7 questions aimed at identifying the type of interventions, the geographical location, and most relevant outcomes.

However, during the analysis we also identified several initiatives addressing leadership in HEI that do not take the gender dimension into account. We have listed these initiatives in a preliminary section to conduct a general reflection about the kind of activities/programmes developed to tackle the leadership of research institutions. The information emerging from these two sources has been organised in 5 regional scopes: global or international initiatives promoted by universities alliances or networks, European initiatives, African initiatives, American Initiatives, and Asian initiatives. The organisation of the results under geographical criteria allowed us to identify some common features and strategies across different contexts, but also some specific initiatives linked to specific geographical contexts. After this geographical classification, we have analysed the kind of initiatives and programmes identified according to their objectives and types of interventions. The aim of this second classification was to check whether the type of interventions and initiatives are influenced by factors such as: institution location, size, nature or discipline. This crossed analysis is in line with the global analysis of the GEARING Roles project about unequal representation of women and men in scientific careers, and the favoured position of men in leadership and decision-making under areas of knowledge, sectors and backgrounds.

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Finally, while the desk research was performed, the team also came across different initiatives to promote female leadership in other sectors such as development, health or business that could be inspiring for the associated partners of the project and other institutions across Europe committed to the promotion of Gender Equality and the implementation of Gender Equality Plans. The identification of these programmes in other sectors could enable a reflection of shared challenges and strategies cross-sectionally to overcome structural resistances to the access of women to leadership positions and decision-making.

The following figure (Figure 1) provides an overview of the results of the desk research. It can be seen how the majority of the practices promoting female leadership in HEIs are developed in North America and Europe, although inspiring practices can be found in other geographical areas.

Figure 1: Geographical distribution of identified inspiring practices of leadership in HEIs.

Getting deeper into the results of the analysis, Table 1 categorises the different interventions identified depending on its main objective. In this sense, the majority of activities are related to training actions, followed by other direct support, mentoring, networking, awareness raising and, as marginal categories, research activities and databases.

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Table 1: Areas of intervention of identified best practices

Type of intervention		
	Programmes and initiatives addressing Leadership in HEI	Programmes addressing female leadership in HEI
Mentoring		7
Networking	1	5
Data Set		1
Research		2
Awareness raising		5
Positive Action/direct support	2	11
Training	7	18

On its side, Table 2 puts emphasis on the geographical distribution of the initiatives. As stated above, Europe leads the number of practices identified in the desk research, with America in second position, followed by Africa, Asia, Arab region, Oceania and a global initiative.

Table 2 : Type of intervention per geographical scope

Type of intervention per geographical scope		
	Programmes and initiatives addressing Leadership in HEI	Programmes addressing female leadership in HEI
Global		1
Europe	7	23
Arab region	1	
Africa		5
America	1	7
Asia	1	3
Oceania		1

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2.1 Programmes and initiatives addressing leadership in HEI

Inspiring Practice 1

U4 Academic Leadership Programme					
Host Institutions	Ghent University, Göttingen University, Groningen University, and Uppsala University				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	International	Source	DA
Brief description	The U4 Academic Leadership programme is a training course for top-level executives in university management which allows university leaders from academia and administration to strengthen their skills in leadership and to learn more about university management. Focusing on strategic leadership, creating international leadership networks and developing and sharing knowledge, skills and experiences of international trends, problems and solutions, the programme consists of sessions that deal with themes such as transparency and accountability in European universities.				
Link	https://www.u4network.eu/index.php/cluster/institutional-management/156-academic-leadership				

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Inspiring Practice 2

Leadership Development Programme					
Host Institution	European Consortium of Innovative Universities - ECIU				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	International	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Launched in 2003, the programme intends to contribute to innovation and change in leadership development at the participating ECIU universities by providing leaders/potential leaders with the possibility to participate in seminars and develop skills such as identifying particular characteristics and challenges of leadership and strategic management in a university context, and developing personal leadership qualities and skills.</p>				
Link	https://www.eciu.org/for-staff/leadership-development-programme				

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Inspiring Practice 3

Arab European Leadership Network in Higher Education – ARELEN					
Host Institutions	Universities in the Arab Region				
Type of intervention	Networking	Country	International	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>This programme is an outcome of the Tempus project "Leadership in Higher Education Management". It provides different programmes and activities aimed at building bridges among universities in the region and implementing capacity building. Among the developed initiatives are the "Leadership for Performance in HE: Building and Leading High Performance Teams", "'Lean Thinking' for Performance in HE", and "Research Leadership and Creating Capacity in Research".</p>				
Link	https://arelen.net/				

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Inspiring Practice 4

European Guidelines and Quality Labels for new Curricula Fostering e-Leadership Skills					
Host Institution	European Commission				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	International	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The Guidelines are the result of 'CEN ICT Skills Workshop', following a formal process to become a CEN Workshop Agreement to be endorsed by the National Members of CEN. Open to education institutions, industry and associations, the initiative launched by the European Commission responds to the inadequacies in the skills market flagged by stakeholders across the EU. Precisely, the institution has begun commissioning studies and launching initiatives designed to foster a full range of skills relating to ICT, "e-skills" and skills gap in the 'e-leadership' domain.</p>				
Link	http://eskills-guide.eu/documents.html				

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Inspiring Practice 5

HUMANE Leadership Training Initiatives					
Host Institution	Heads of University Management and Administration Network in Europe - HUMANE				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	International	Source	DA
Brief description	HUMANE consists of an international association whose aims are to build international networks to foster innovation in higher education services and to drive professional excellence in higher education management. Besides supporting the professional development of current executive leaders within the HE sector, it also provides programmes to promising senior staff such as seminars and conferences, study visits, residential schools and the design of professional pathways on research management, management of impact, human resources management, etc.				
Link	http://www.humane.eu/home/				

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Inspiring Practice 6

Poland's new autonomy and governance framework for higher education					
Host Institution	Ministry of National Education				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Intervention	Country	Poland	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Polish policy makers have developed a higher education reform in the country aimed at achieving greater university autonomy, strategic governance, leadership, management and operational efficiency. The new law is intended to provide higher education institutions with autonomy to determine their internal governance and organisation structures. Among the new practices, the policy strengthens the role of the rector, provides a new funding model in which funds are awarded to universities rather than to their organisational units. In addition, universities will have more autonomy to allocate the combined subsidy they will receive for teaching and research. Finally, while maintaining its academic ethos, the policy creates new dynamics and stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship in universities, therefore opening more room for managerial decisions and stimulating innovation on business partnerships.</p>				
Link	http://efficiency.eua.eu/good-practices				

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Inspiring Practice 7

Dean School					
Host Institution	Universities Norway				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Norway	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The programme is part of a strategic initiative to develop and strengthen leadership training in higher education institutions, operating in conjunction with institution's own research management and institutional leadership programmes. Dean School is focused on university and university college deans, as well as on department heads of the largest institutions and is aimed at enhancing participant's skills and developing their leadership role.</p>				
Link	http://efficiency.eua.eu/good-practices				

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Inspiring Practice 8

Pakistani Educational Leadership Project - PELP					
Host Institution	Plymouth State University				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Pakistan	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>PELP is a project funded by the US Department of State which is designed to contribute to the growth and development of the educational system in Pakistan through the introduction of teacher-trainers, educational administrators and other educational leaders to new methods and ideas. Among its goals and actions, the project provides science educators with leadership skills to effect change at the grassroots through the development of trainings primarily focused on educational leadership, environmental stewardship, and cultural heritage preservation.</p>				
Link	http://docplayer.net/148925693-Pakistani-educational-leadership-project.html				

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Inspiring Practice 9

Diversity Plan 2019-2024					
Host Institution	Meise Botanic Garden				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Belgium	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The Botanic Garden has included "respect for diversity" as one of its values and wants to structurally anchor diversity in its personnel policy. To this end, the Botanic Garden has included actions related to diversity in the business plan and in the culture plan ("diversity"):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Recruiting young or not yet graduated students as part of the Agency's core tasks to implement the objectives of the target groups (ongoing action) · Raising awareness among staff members and managers about diversity issues and diversity actions · Include diversity in training plan · Querying diversity in staff satisfaction surveys · Developing the role of coach (colleague female/ male) in the workplace · Being open to and capturing suggestions from staff members about diversity · Measures in the event of adjustments to work equipment / working conditions for people with a disability. <p>Additionally the Garden is part of the Science4Refugees program via EURAXESS.</p>				

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Inspiring Practice 10

Lidera - Programa de Formación de Jóvenes en Liderazgo					
Host Institution	Universidad Católica Andrés Bello, Instituto de Estudios Superior de Administración y Universidad Metropolitana				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Venezuela	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The programme is aimed at strengthening the capacities and generating relational skills of young people from different regions of the country, with profiles of social, cultural, political, business and student action.</p> <p>Participants are selected annually among young people between the ages of 18 and 30 from all states of the country, who have a leadership profile and potential to teamwork and networking.</p>				
Link	https://futuropresente.com.ve/lidera/				

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2.2 Programmes and initiatives addressing female leadership in HEI

2.2.1. Global

Inspiring Practice 1

AcademiaNet					
Host Institutions	Robert Bosch Stiftung and Spektrum der Wissenschaft				
Type of intervention	Dataset	Country	International	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>With the goal of tackling the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions in academia and the sciences, AcademiaNet is a tool that provides numerous profiles of excellent women academics from every discipline, making them more visible and easily accessible. Initially exposing profiles of German-speaking women academics, the portal has been gradually internationalised and expanded, containing now information both in German and in English. Since 2012, the portal has become a European database for those searching for suitable female candidates for influential academic and scientific positions.</p>				
Link	http://www.academia-net.org/project/				

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2.2.2. Europe

Inspiring Practice 2

European Women Rectors Association - EWORA					
Host Institution	EWORA				
Type of intervention	Networking	Country	International	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The association was established in 2015 with the aim of promoting the role of women in leadership positions in the academic sector and to advocate gender equality in higher education and research at European and international scales. Its focuses revolve, among others, around the development of strategies and policies that encourage women academics to target leadership positions, the creation of opportunities for increasing women's representation in higher education, research and decision-making positions, and the balanced participation of women and men in academic leadership.</p>				
Link	https://www.ewora.org/				

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Inspiring Practice 3

AdvanceHE					
Host Institution	Universities UK and GuildHE				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	United Kingdom	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Founded in a joint initiative between Universities UK and GuildHE, AdvanceHE is a company aimed at improving the management, governance and leadership skills of existing and future higher education leaders in the UK. It promotes research and practical initiatives on equality in the academic sector and, based on the analysis of the unequal status of women and men in academic positions, positive actions have been taken to address this imbalance in staff recruitment, selection and promotion processes. Among others, actions involve the possibility of appointing women over men in tie-break situations where there is an underrepresentation of women, as well as measures to avoid the distinction between male and female candidates in interviews. Moreover, also aimed at addressing the gender imbalance in higher education institutions, formal mentoring programmes have been implemented to support the progress of women's careers in the sector.</p>				
Link	www.advance-he.ac.uk				

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Inspiring Practice 4

The Gender, Leadership and Inclusion Centre (GLIC)					
Host Institution	Cranfield School of management				
Type of intervention	Research	Country	United Kingdom	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The Gender, Leadership and Inclusion Centre (GLIC) bridges research and practice in the areas of gender, leadership and inclusion at work. It is aimed at ensuring an evidence-based approach to attaining every woman's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels in professional life. The program develops actions such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International and applied research agenda in contemporary developments on gender diversity, including intersectionality, privilege and inclusive leadership. • Producing academic research in partnership with organisations, policy partners and research councils. • Collaborating with industry to identify and analyse gender diversity issues pertinent to industry and practitioners. <p>To achieve the goals of the programme, GLIC provides a variety of projects such as the Female FTSE Index, the Female FTSE Board Report, the Women to Watch, among others.</p>				
Link	https://www.cranfield.ac.uk/som/expertise/changing-world-of-work/gender-leadership-and-inclusion-centre				

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Inspiring Practice 5

The Leicester Academic Career Map					
Host Institution	University of Leicester				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	United Kingdom	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Aimed at transforming the University's promotion processes to make them more appealing to women and inclusive, in addition to recognising the central importance of research and teaching, the Leicester Academic Career Map gives a special attention to the explicit recognition of contributions to enterprise, engagement, citizenship and leadership - areas that are often undertaken by women but had not been clearly rewarded through the University's promotion routes in the past. The map specifies what individuals need to achieve in order to be considered for promotion and focuses upon the impact that achievement has had upon others. In order to sustain change, the institution continuously provides a pipeline to progression through development opportunities including leadership training, return-to-career fellowships, mentoring and coaching. Finally, as a HeForShe Champion, the University became an attractive employer for women, providing on-site childcare, promoting flexible working options and tackling a gender pay gap.</p>				
Link	<p>https://www2.le.ac.uk/offices/equalities-unit</p> <p>https://www.heforshe.org/sites/default/files/2018-10/HeForShe%20Emerging%20Solutions%20Report%202018%20-%20Full%20Report.pdf</p>				

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Inspiring Practice 6

Identification, Development, Advancement and Support - IDAS					
Host Institution	Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions				
Type of intervention	Networking Training Mentoring	Country	Sweden	Source	DA
Brief description	Created from a cooperative effort between several national institutions, the IDAS was a leadership development project aimed at increasing the number of women in leadership positions at universities and university colleges in Sweden. By launching measures such as the establishment of local, regional and national networks, competence-building seminars, leadership development and mentoring programmes, surveys and reports, the programme encouraged and supported women academics to pursue leadership and administrative careers in higher education institutions.				
Link	https://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:702842/FULLTEXT01.pdf				

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Inspiring Practice 7

Gender Initiative for Excellence - GENIE					
Host Institution	Chalmers University of Technology of Gothenburg				
Type of intervention	Awareness Raising	Country	Sweden	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Launched on 1 January 2019 as a strategic plan to address gender inequality in the faculty, GENIE is a long-term programme aimed at implementing concrete changes in academic culture, systems and processes. Holding the final goal of increasing the proportion of women professors from 17% today to 40% by 2029, it proposes a combination of bottom-up and top-down efforts to redress gender inequality and set up tailor-made activities for each department. Through such actions, the programme intends to remove obstacles that hamper women's careers, creating working environments that are diverse and inclusive and support excellence in research and teaching. Priorities such as the direct recruitment of top female researchers are part of the strategic plan, as well as the incorporation of gender aspects into all statistics and a broader sharing of data concerning pay and qualifications in promotions at the institution.</p>				
Link	http://www.chalmers.se/en/about-chalmers/Chalmers-for-a-sustainable-future/initiatives-for-gender-equality/gender-initiative-for-excellence/Pages/default.aspx				

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Inspiring Practice 8

Action plan for gender mainstreaming at Karlstad University 2017-2019					
Host Institution	Karlstad University				
Type of intervention	Awareness Raising Training	Country	Sweden	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>Following government directives in 2016, Karlstad University developed an ambitious plan to gender mainstream its operations. This plan focused on four areas: (1) Teaching, (2) Research, (3) Management and support processes, and (4) Regulation and overall governance. In the case of management and support processes, the aim was to have gender equality permeating routines and attitudes related to leadership, skills supply, working conditions, work environment and administrative support.</p> <p>Several development needs were identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Gendered expectations, as well as formal and informal power structures have to be considered from the perspective of gender equality. b) A gender-equal approach has to be taken to systematic work environment improvement, mapping and measures. c) Administrative routines, recruitment and conditions for leadership have to be gender equal. d) A gender-equal, norm-critical approach has to be integrated into leadership development programmes and into courses in teaching and learning in higher education. <p>Furthermore a number of actions to be implemented were proposed, specifying what structures were responsible:</p>				

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">· Shedding light on gendered expectations and conditions of appointed leaders and suggest measures (Deans and university directors)· Shedding light on the recruitment of leaders and suggest measures from a gender-equality perspective (Deans and university directors) <p>Training heads and chairs of boards receive in gender-equal communication, gender-equal meetings and norm-critical perspectives (Head of HR).</p>
Link	http://intra.kau.se/dokument/upload/C10B9C4E056ca1959CruDE247775/8751664700000000000000000600.pdf

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Inspiring Practice 9

AKKA Leadership Programme					
Host Institution	Lund University				
Type of intervention	Awareness Raising	Country	Sweden	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Launched in 2004, the AKKA is a gender-integrated leadership programme that aims at raising gender knowledge and awareness and providing methods and tools for structural change to achieve sustainable gender equality. Providing short and long-term goals, the programme initially focused on encouraging female researchers working at Lund University to apply for deans and vice-deans, in order to further achieve the final goal of increasing the number of female leaders at the institution.</p> <p>In addition to focusing on the number of women in leadership roles, the programme also implemented awareness campaigns and provided methods and tools to pursue structural changes, involving both women and men in such actions. To this end, seminars, workshops and a project work were designed and serve as discussion forums where participants exchange experiences and knowledge. Precisely in the project work, the purpose is to identify and analyse particular discriminatory practices from an integrated gender and diversity perspective, pursuing possibilities for change through constructive solutions.</p> <p>Since its launch the programme has been offered annually for senior scholars at the university and, among other positive impacts, it has increased the number of women in leading positions, contributed to their visibility as potential leaders, increased willingness of both genders to undertake leadership positions, and developed tools to deal with resistance to gender issues and for change management.</p>				

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Link	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/good-practices/sweden/akka-leadership-programme
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Inspiring Practice 10

KIF Committee					
Host Institutions	Kilden/Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research and The Norwegian Association of Higher Education Institutions				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Norway	Source	DA
Brief description	Established in 2004, the KIF Committee is focused on the improvement of gender balance at universities, university colleges and research institutes, and provides support and recommendations on measures contributing to gender balance and diversity in the Norwegian research sector. Among its priorities, the actions are focused on including gender perspectives in research, developing recruitment measures that encourage gender-balanced processes, fostering career-promoting measures with attention to how to lay a foundation for gender equality in academia, enhancing diversity in the sector and compiling measures targeted towards students in order to achieve a more gender-balanced student body.				
Link	http://kifinfo.no/en/content/committee-gender-balance-and-diversity-research-kif-0				

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Inspiring Practice 11

Gender Equality at NTNU					
Host Institution	Norwegian University of Science and Technology				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Norway	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>NTNU has adopted an internal policy that encourages and promotes qualified women in academic and administrative positions. Female researchers can take advantage of a variety of programmes and services such as start packages for women in permanent scientific positions in male-dominated departments, stipends to aid women in associate professor positions to become full professors, and mentoring programmes for women who are in recruited and associate professor positions.</p>				
Links	<p>https://www.ntnu.edu/gender-equality</p> <p>https://www.ntnu.edu/documents/139226/1106930/action-plan-to-improve-gender-balance-2014-2016-ntnu.pdf/</p>				

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Inspiring Practice 12

Action Plan for: Equal Opportunities, Inclusion and Diversity 2016/2020					
Host Institution	University of Agder				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Norway	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Focusing on gender equal opportunities among staff members, the programme holds measures ranging from gender balance in all departments and positions, including in management roles, to equal salaries to both genders. By 2020, the goal of the action is to achieve at least 40% of each gender in all management groups at Faculty and department level. To this end, specific measures such as ensuring that both women and men are amongst the applicants for management positions, actively encouraging female department heads to apply to the dean trainee arrangement, are part of the actions.</p>				
Link	http://kifinfo.no/sites/default/files/actionplanforequalopportunities2cinclusionanddiversity2016-2020.pdf				

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Inspiring Practice 13

"Women towards the Top-UiS in Movement and Balance" -Project					
Host Institution	University of Stavanger				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Norway	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The University of Stavanger had 45.2% women in associate professorships, but only 21.2% female professors at the beginning of 2015. Through "Women towards the top - UiS in movement and balance", the university started a long-term commitment with a focus on awareness and accountability of the line management to increase the numbers of females in top research positions. This was the starting point for the University of Stavanger to implement a number of organisational and personal measures to improve its gender statistics, and especially focus on how the university could lift already employed female associated professor-to-professor level competency. It has been an important part of the project to include leaders, allocate funds to the selected groups of women participating in the project and to have this as part of the internal Leader development program to ensure these differences are top of mind in appraisal interview and when hiring. At the starting point of the project, the percentage of female professors was as low as 20 percent, three years later this number had increased to 35 percent. UiS continued to support the project after the 3-year project period with economic support from the Norwegian Research Council was over in 2018, the goal for the next period is to have 45 % female professors in 2022.</p>				
Link					

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Inspiring Practice 14

Programme on Gender Balance in Senior Positions and Research Management (BALANSE)					
Host Institution	Research Council of Norway				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Norway	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The Programme on Gender Balance in Senior Positions and Research Management (BALANSE) is a policy-oriented programme at the Research Council with a ten-year programme period (2012–2022). The main objective of the programme is to promote gender equality and gender balance in Norwegian research.</p> <p>The gender imbalance is a systemic challenge that the institutions cannot solve individually. The BALANSE programme provides incentives to institutions to take on greater responsibility for improving gender balance.</p> <p>The programme seeks to promote gender equality and gender balance in Norwegian research, with particular focus on increasing the proportion of women in senior academic and research management positions, helping to bring about structural and cultural change in the research system to facilitate this.</p> <p>BALANSE funding may be sought by universities, university colleges, research institutes, and research-intensive trade and industry. An example of a project implemented in the University of Stavanger with partial support of this funding programme can be found in the inspiring practice 13 above.</p>				
Link	https://www.forskingsradet.no/en/about-the-research-council/programmes/balanse/				

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Inspiring Practice 15

Action Plan for Improving the Gender Balance in Academic Positions					
Host Institution	Norwegian School of Economics (NHH)				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Norway	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The NHH Action Plan for gender balance bases itself on the need to integrate gender equality focus into the School's core activities in research, teaching and dissemination. General objectives include: promoting an organisational culture and a working environment that is inclusive and fair for both genders; organising research, teaching and dissemination actions that are attractive to both men and women and gives employees of both genders equal opportunities; and implementing an active recruitment policy that equalises a skewed gender selection and prevents indirect discrimination. Measures such as ensuring the presence of women and men in lectures in all programmes and at all levels, using both genders in the media, balancing the composition of decision-making boards, councils and committees, and using the School's salary policy as a means to achieve the targets for the recruitment of women make part of the plan.</p>				
Link	https://www.nhh.no/globalassets/om-nhh/likestilling/action-plan-for-improving-the-gender-balance-in-academic-positions.pdf				

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Inspiring Practice 16

Actions to foster women leadership					
Host Institution	Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia, IBEC				
Type of intervention	Mentoring	Country	Spain	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer mentoring for women Principal Investigators (PIs): Women PIs of 3 different research Institutes meet 2-3 hours every 2 months for peer mentoring. They are guided by an expert in mentoring schemes. Increasing the number of women in decision making bodies: Every year on when someone drops off from the International Scientific Committee (ISC), IBEC will propose the names of different women. 2 Women scientists have joined recently the ISC. 				
Link					

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Inspiring Practice 17

Grant to the mothers of Science					
Host Institution	Barcelona Institute of Science & Technology (BIST) and Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia (IBEC)				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Spain	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	BIST support women scientists who have the ambition and potential to reach a leading position in research and are fulfilling maternity responsibilities at the same time. This program aims to address the gap that exists between the number of women in the BIST Community who are research associates or senior post-doctoral researchers (41%) and the percentage of women who are group leaders (only 15%). The 10 Supporting grants and the coaching program recognize the value and excellent research done by these scientists and support them in their career transition.				
Link	http://bist.eu/women-in-science/				

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Inspiring Practice 18

Cátedra on Equal Gender					
Host Institution	University of Zaragoza				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support Training	Country	Spain	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>Institutional & Enterprises Chairs (Cátedras) are a tool to establish a permanent collaboration between the University of Zaragoza (UZ) and Enterprises and Organisations to obtain research, development and innovation results.</p> <p>The Cátedra on Equal Gender UZ was created on 21/07/2007 in collaboration with the Aragonian Woman Institute (Aragon Government). Its teaching and education activities are aimed at university students but also at the teaching and administration staff. These are implemented mainly in the Faculty of Social Sciences and Employment and in the Faculty of Philosophy and Literature and include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Master degree on Gender Equality · Courses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gender equality in at the Public Administration ○ Enterpreunership, leadership and equal gender on the 21st Century ○ Teaching Staff on equal gender · Workshops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Feminist studies ○ Congresses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ On violence against women ○ On Work-life balance ○ On Maternity and professional environment · Prizes and contests: 				

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Feminist research for equality○ Publicity contest in recognition of responsibility and gender equality○ Women entrepreneurs· Regular conferences <p>A detailed list of recent activities can be found in the link provided (in Spanish).</p>
Link	https://otri.unizar.es/es/catedra/catedra-sobre-igualdad-y-genero

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Inspiring Practice 19

Diversity and equality					
Host Institution	University of Copenhagen				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Denmark	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The University of Copenhagen has an international work and study environment based on values such as democracy, openness and equal opportunities. The University is an inclusive workplace that wishes to attract the most talented students and staff regardless of personal background. The University is keen to create a tolerant culture where everyone is treated equally, and where diversity is a strength, not a challenge. Based on the University's overall strategy, Talent and collaboration – Strategy 2023, the University puts focus on equality and diversity. The strategy focuses on ensuring that the University of Copenhagen can continue to attract, develop and retain scientific talents. The University wants to provide a diverse and inclusive working and study environment, where critical thinking and diversity go hand in hand. As part of this goal a "diversity officer" has been hired last year.</p>				
Link	https://about.ku.dk/strategy2023/unified-university/				

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Inspiring Practice 20

Gender Plan for the gender policy application					
Host Institution	University of Camerino				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Italy	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The plan includes a first review on the University's gender balance focusing on students, researcher, and administrative staff. Then it underlines relevant actions to be implemented in order to systematically monitor the organisation.</p> <p>These includes promoting pilot projects to push the women empowerment in research as well as the presentation of role model supporting the younger research in being involved on STEM activities. Last but not least, the use of Italian language has to be pushed to refer in both male and female the roles. Documents have to be revised and reconsidered to balance language use.</p>				
Link					

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Inspiring Practice 21

Women Professors Forum (WPF)					
Host Institution	Ruhr University Bochum				
Type of intervention	Networking	Country	Germany	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The Women Professors Forum (WPF), an association of around 140 female professors at the university, is an important forum that has made its voice heard on the campus on issues of gender equality. In the run-up to the last elections to the central university bodies, this network was very active in putting female candidates on the electoral lists. As a result, an average of 50% of all central bodies at the university are women. Half of all central bodies are chaired by a woman. Further information on the WPF can be found under the link below.</p>				
Link	https://www.ruhr-uni-bochum.de/women-prof-forum/strategies/index.html.en				

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Inspiring Practice 22

Gender equality in recruitment procedure for professors					
Host Institution	University of Bern				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Switzerland	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>To increase the number of female professors, the University of Bern has implemented a number of measures for recruitment procedures of future professors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines for Gender Equality in recruitment procedures (2019) • The Office for Gender Equality has produced a short film "female professors wanted", which is shown in every commission to sensitise for gender equality issues and hidden bias. • A gender equality delegate of the Office of Gender Equality and a gender equality delegate of the faculty are present in every recruitment committee for professorships. • The University has developed guidelines on job-sharing for professors to foster job-sharing on the professorial level. 				
Link	https://www.unibe.ch/university/portrait/self_image/equality/focuses/recruitment_procedure/index_eng.html				

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Inspiring Practice 23

Application of FESTA Handbook					
Host Institution	Fondazione Bruno Kessler				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Italy	Source	EURAXESS
Brief description	Recruitment policies of the institution are aligned to the FESTA Handbook by: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Always have at least 1 female member in the selection committee 2. If 2 candidates score the same mark, priority in the hiring procedure is given to the female candidate. 				
Link	https://hr.fbk.eu/en/festa-project				

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Inspiring Practice 24

AKADEME					
Host Institution	University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)				
Type of intervention	Training Networking	Country	Spain	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>AKADEME targets women in middle and top management at University of the Basque Country, with the aim of improving leadership abilities and promoting its participation in a network of support among participants to motivate and enhance collective empowerment to access or stay in responsibility positions.</p> <p>It is designs as a practical programme that combines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-site sessions - Online training platform - Assignments to put the knowledge into practice - Coaching sessions 				
Link	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/akademe/home				

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2.2.3 Other regions of the world

Africa

Inspiring Practice 25

KENYATTA University HeForShe experience					
Host Institution	Kenyatta University				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Kenya	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Kenyatta University has joined the UN Women's HeForShe movement to address critical policy issues and look for changes in the course of leadership. Aligning with the existing priorities of the IMPACT Universities that compose the movement, Kenyatta University has contributed with a new global view and committed itself to achieving a gender-balanced leadership. Moreover, the University proposed itself to embed gender equality into the very DNA of the institution and to address gender-based violence across its campuses.</p>				
Link	https://www.heforshe.org/en/heforshe-impact-10x10x10-parity-report-launch				

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Inspiring Practice 26

Higher Education Leadership Programme - HELP					
Host Institution	CODESRIA				
Type of intervention	Research Training	Country	Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, Tanzania and Uganda	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Launched in 2011, the HELP programme sought to support research networks, policy forums and publications to document and provide an understanding of transformations underway with regard to the governance and leadership of higher education institutions in Africa. The works were developed through the implementation of policy debates, research groups, methodological workshops and conferences revolving around themes such as gender aspects of governance transformations, emergent practices in the working of governance bodies-councils, senates and faculty boards, and the role of Faculty/academics in the engagement in the leadership and academic processes at the institutions.</p>				
Link	https://www.codesria.org/carnegie/bonjour-tout-le-monde/				

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Inspiring Practice 27

Higher Education Leadership Programs for Women.HERS					
Host Institution	The School of Women and Gender Studies of Makerere University				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Uganda	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The School of Women and Gender Studies of Makerere University has implemented short and long-term strategies with focus on gender equality to improve the representation of women in senior and management level positions in the higher education sector in the country.</p> <p>Thinking in how gender is being treated in the construction of this new leadership, and how this can help to promote the changes in higher education organisations, the project suggests: a) affirmative action programmes that can help change the organisational culture of a university to one that encourages women’s participation; b) a specific Task Group that identifies and lobbies for the necessary required changes on gender equality; c) a colloquium of senior women managers in higher education, including training and support network for senior women and; d) networks for women in universities to help tackle gender inequalities through the offer of several opportunities that can benefit women from different sectors such as peer mentoring.</p>				
Link	<p>https://onthinktanks.org/articles/strategies-to-increase-women-in-higher-education-leadership-in-public-universities-in-uganda/</p> <p>https://womenstudies.mak.ac.ug/</p>				

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Inspiring Practice 28

The Higher Education Resource Services-East Africa (HERS-EA) Academy					
Host Institution	The Higher Education Resource Services-East Africa (HERS-EA) Academy				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	East Africa (Burundi, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, South Sudan, Tanzania and Uganda)	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>HERS-EA is a sister organisation of HERS, providing leadership and management training for women in Higher Education Institutions in East Africa (Burundi, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, South Sudan, Tanzania and Uganda) through an intensive training that is specifically tailored to strengthen the knowledge and skills of women, enabling them to assume institutional leadership roles competitively. Through the implementation projects such as "Developing Effective Partnerships in Higher Education for Women" and "The Power of Mentoring", the project addresses issues such as personal development, leadership, fundraising for research and publication, and institutional awareness.</p>				
Link	https://www.hers-ea.org/				

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Inspiring Practice 29

HERS-SA					
Host Institution	Higher Education Resource Services (HERS)				
Type of intervention	Awareness Raising	Country	South Africa	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>HERS-SA is an independent Chapter of HERS dedicated to the advancement and leadership development of women in the higher education sector. It contributes to the career and leadership development of women employed in the higher education sector by maintaining a flow of information between women in higher education, circulating information about development opportunities, advocacy, gender research and jobs in higher education, facilitating networking between women in higher education institutions, supporting research collaborations into, and advocacy for, gender equity in higher education.</p>				
Link	http://www.hers-sa.org.za/				

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America

Inspiring Practice 30

GME Women in Medicine Leadership Council					
Host Institution	Stanford University - School of Medicine				
Type of intervention	Mentoring Training	Country	United States of America	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Aimed at empowering women and building a community among women trainees and those who support them, the GME (Graduate Medical Education) Women in Medicine Leadership Council - a subcommittee of the GME Diversity Committee - acts on projects focused on women in medicine (residents, fellows and faculty members). Precisely, it develops workshops on career trajectory, negotiation and unconscious bias. In addition, it provides resources to staff such as support to deal with harassment, child care, back-up care, lactation rooms, and maternity and paternity leave.</p>				
Link	https://med.stanford.edu/gme.html				

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Inspiring Practice 31

APA Leadership Institute for Women in Psychology - LIWP					
Host Institution	APA Committee on Women in Psychology				
Type of intervention	Mentoring Training	Country	United States of America	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Holding the goal of supporting and empowering women psychologists as leaders, the major focus of the institute is to ensure that leadership training opportunities are available for mid-career and senior women psychologists in all of their diversities. Its purpose is to provide women psychologists with the knowledge skills necessary to compete for leadership/senior management positions in academic, practice and other professional setting. Moreover, the institute pursues diversity amongst women psychologists in academia, practice and other leadership positions, creates networks of women psychologists in leadership/senior management positions in varied professional settings, and document the career movement, professional advancement and the perceived impact of the LIWP among participants.</p>				
Link	https://www.apa.org/pi/women/programs/leadership/				

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Inspiring Practice 32

Women's Leadership Development Institute - WLDI					
Host Institution	Council for Christian Colleges & Universities (CCCU)				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	United States	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The action is a year-long programme targeted toward women leaders across the CCCU campuses. The programme provides participants with individually-tailored shadowing experience with a senior-level leader on another CCCU campus and professional networking with other current and emerging leaders. In addition, participants receive an introduction to cutting-edge leadership literature and research and a one-to-one meeting with a Resource Team member to outline a year-long Professional Development Plan.</p>				
Link	https://www.cccu.org/programs-services/institutes/wldi/				

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Inspiring Practice 33

LEADERS Institute					
Host Institution	American Association for Women in Community Colleges (AAWCC)				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	United States	Source	DA
Brief description	The LEADERS Institute is a five day experiential workshop that promotes the development of women's leadership skills and qualities at every level in community college education and administration. The institute is designed to prepare women leaders for career opportunities, career advancement, and executive-level leadership positions, including the presidency.				
Link	https://www.aawccnatl.org/leaders-institute				

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Inspiring Practice 34

Academic Women's Association - AWA					
Host Institution	University of Calgary				
Type of intervention	Awareness Raising	Country	Canada	Source	DA
Brief description	The Association is aimed at advancing academic women's career development from earliest stages to post-career, through advocacy and raising awareness of women's issues in collaboration with other equity associations in the campus.				
Link	https://www.ucalgary.ca/awa/				

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Inspiring Practice 35

BRIDGES					
Host Institution	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill				
Type of intervention	Training Mentoring	Country	United States	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>BRIDGES is an inclusive professional development programme to strengthen the leadership capabilities of women in the academia. It is designed to help women to identify, understand and build their leadership roles in the academy. To this end, the programme provides actions for women to develop insights into leadership, with a particular focus on the special skills and attributes women bring to their leadership roles, refine and improve their cross-cultural communication skills, among others. Through such actions, BRIDGE aims to explore the exercise of leadership capacities to their fullest, in order to transform institutions and fields of expertise and provide models for transforming the understanding of leadership in higher education.</p>				
Link	https://fridaycenter.unc.edu/friday-center-home/professional-education/bridges/				

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Inspiring Practice 36

Women in Academic Leadership					
Host Institution	University of Manitoba				
Type of intervention	Training Mentoring	Country	Canada	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The programme consists of a five-day residential programme of workshops and mentorship from the Centre for Higher Education Research and Development (CHERD) to enhance participant's executive leadership potential. It is designed for early to mid-level academic leaders and is led by facilitators and a group of mentors who guide interactive sections.</p>				
Link	https://umextended.ca/women-in-academic-leadership/				

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Asia

Inspiring Practice 37

Connecttask					
Host Institution	Asian University for Women				
Type of intervention	Networking	Country	Bangladesh	Source	DA
Brief description	Asian University for Women is an independent, regional institution dedicated to women's education and leadership development which focuses on building network and supporting the empowerment of current and future women leaders through liberal arts and sciences education.				
Link	https://asian-university.org http://connecttask.com/tag/chancellor-of-the-asian-university-for-women-in-chittagong-bangladesh/				

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Inspiring Practice 38

UGC Capacity Development workshops for women managers in HE					
Host Institution	The Department of Electrical Engineering, Jamia Millia Islamia				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	India	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>In 2006 the Department of Electrical Engineering, Jamia Millia Islamia, organised a UGC (University Grant Commission) workshop on Capacity Building of Women Managers in Higher Education and launched a programme for women in higher education in the academic and administrative stream that seeks to increase the percentage of women at decision-making levels in Indian universities and colleges. The program invites universities to nominate women at middle and high-level positions to undergo the programme.</p>				
Link	<p>https://www.jmi.ac.in/bulletinboard/press-releases/latest/UGC_workshop_on_Capacity_Building_of_Women_Managers_in_Higher_Education-397</p>				

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Inspiring Practice 39

Promoting Women at the Institute				
Host Institution	Holon Institute for Technology			
Type of intervention		Country	Israel	Source EURAXESS
Brief description	<p>The Institute’s 2015-2025 Strategic Plan includes as one its objectives “Promoting Women at the Institute”. This objective will be achieved by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting women in the fields of technology and design, while creating supportive frameworks for honors students, including designated study scholarships, supportive professional counseling during their studies, and female mentors who will guide the students during their studies. • Launching a review into how women are faring in different faculties, so as to discover special needs and find, as far as possible, institutional remedies for any problems that might be discovered. • Highlighting information relevant to women's academic promotion, including information about scholarships and grants, events, rights, and more. • Seeking to secure gender balance among faculty members, by removing obstacles preventing women from promotion, if such are discovered. • Providing a satisfactory supportive environment for female faculty members and administrators, including scheduling special conferences, an online women's forum, and more 			
Link	https://www.hit.ac.il/sites/en/StrategicPlan2015/PlanSketch			

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Oceania

Inspiring Practice 40

Women in Leadership at Otago Programme - WiLO					
Host Institution	University of Otago				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	New Zealand	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The Women in Leadership at Otago Programme (WiLO) explores the qualities and skills associated with leadership and management for all women from all Otago campuses. To do so, the programme focuses on the context for leadership at the University of Otago, developing leadership skills and planning on-going professional development as a leader.</p>				
Link	https://www.otago.ac.nz/humanresources/training/otago064400.html				

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3. Leadership programmes in other sectors

Inspiring Practice 41

INSEAD's Women Leaders Programme					
Host Institution	The Business School for the World				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	France	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>INSEAD's Women Leaders Programme creates a space where women executives have an opportunity to come together and share their leadership experiences in a learning environment where their personal aspects are also taken into consideration, given that those represent significantly the challenges encountered by women throughout their career, and creates a network of today's senior women leaders. The actions are focused on teaching women with leadership techniques and are guided by a professional coach in order to develop and plan goals for personal and professional development and meet a community of women in senior leadership roles.</p>				
Link	https://www.insead.edu/executive-education/leadership/women-leaders-programme				

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Inspiring Practice 42

Female Leadership Development Programme					
Host Institution	Budapest Bank				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Hungary	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>A Female Leadership Development Programme was launched in 2011. The one-year programme's aim is to help women middle managers to reach their career goals. Four of the 11 participating women employees are now working in a higher position or as a leader of a more complex area.</p>				
Link	http://www.budapestbank.hu/				

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Inspiring Practice 43

Women in Football Leadership Programme					
Host Institution	UEFA				
Type of intervention	Training Mentoring	Country	Europe	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The Women in Football Leadership Programme is designed for women in football who have the potential and motivation to progress into senior leadership positions within their organisation or are already in such roles. Participants work on and discuss aspects of leadership, while also focusing heavily on self-awareness and how this can support their career development. With the coaching included during the programme week, participants are challenged in both personal and professional aspects. Organised in collaboration with FIFA, the programme also provides a platform for exchange and networking between participants with a rich variety of backgrounds.</p>				
Link	https://uefaacademy.com/wflp/				

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Inspiring Practice 44

FIFA Female Leadership Development Programme					
Host Institution	FIFA & THNK				
Type of intervention	Training Mentoring	Country	Global	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>The FIFA Women’s Leadership Development Programme was launched in 2015 with the aim of identifying, supporting and developing female leaders and role models in football. The long term outcome, it was hoped, would deliver more women in senior decision-making positions.</p> <p>The programme combines training sessions with a mentorship programme and coaching designed to strengthen their ability to lead in the world of football. A key part of the curriculum is a personal project (called “the Accelerator”), chosen by each participant, that is designed to have a significant impact on the world of football and which stands as testimony to their leadership vision.</p>				
Link	<p>https://www.fifa.com/womens-football/news/fifa-women-s-leadership-programme-delivering-dividends-down-under</p> <p>FIFA Female Leadership Development Programme</p>				

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Inspiring Practice 45

Global Board Ready Women					
Host Institution	Forté Foundation				
Type of intervention	Dataset	Country	Global	Source	DA
Brief description	Forté's official database and list of Global Board Ready Women, offers headhunters, Chairs and boards a central place to locate women who are qualified to sit on a board when they are looking for new board members.				
Link	http://www.fortefoundation.org/site/PageServer?pagename=women_boards				

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Inspiring Practice 46

Notable Women Programme					
Host Institution	AMZ				
Type of intervention	Positive Action / Direct Support	Country	Australia	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Notable Women is a programme developed by AMZ that focuses on building confidence and capability of senior female leaders to build their presence as experts with both traditional and social media. In recent times, the programme has been expanded to leaders deeper in the organisation.</p>				
Link	https://www.anz.com.au/about-us/sustainability/workplace-participation-diversity/gender/				

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Inspiring Practice 47

RiiSE					
Host Institution	AccorHotels Group				
Type of intervention	Mentoring	Country	Global	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Six years after its creation, the WAAG network is taking a new step by improving the Group's commitment to gender equality with a new goal: diversity, as a key driver of collective performance.</p> <p>Renamed "RiiSE" and open to both men and women, this network is active across five continents via the mobilization of strong regional communities. Its action is based in particular on the sharing of knowledge through a mentoring program, with 900 pairs in some 20 countries in 2018, on the promotion of especially female talent to positions of responsibility, and on combatting all forms of discrimination.</p> <p>Another of RiiSE network's core beliefs is that no progress can be made in terms of gender equality, fairness and diversity without the support of men, who currently represent 50% of the network's members.</p> <p>In addition to mentoring and the promotion of diversity, RiiSE will strive to combat stereotypes, everyday sexism, and sexual harassment.</p>				
Link	https://group.accor.com/en/careers/our-philosophy/culture-of-inclusion				

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Inspiring Practice 48

KPMG WTalent Programme					
Host Institution	KPMG Spain				
Type of intervention	Training	Country	Spain	Source	DA
Brief description	WTalent Programme focuses of the individual in order to help each women to enhance all its growing and leadership potential within the company, with the aim of increasing the number of female partners (top management position) a 5 per cent by 2021.				
Link	https://home.kpmg/es/es/home/sala-de-prensa/notas-de-prensa/2019/04/kpmg-dell-promoveran-liderazgo-femenino.html				

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Inspiring Practice 49

Women in Networking					
Host Institution	Enagás				
Type of intervention	Networking	Country	Spain	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>Women in Networking is an initiative aimed at boosting teamwork for the professional development of women within the company. It consists on several networking events around a key topics. In the first session, leadership, diversity and networking were addressed.</p>				
Link	<p>https://www.enagas.es/WEBCORP-static/AzulYVerde/AYV_32/en-equipo.html</p>				

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Inspiring Practice 50

Association of Women Executives and CEOs					
Host Institution	EJE&CON				
Type of intervention	Networking	Country	Spain	Source	DA
Brief description	<p>EJE&CON brings together high-level women executives with the mission of promoting the presence of women in senior management and boards of directors through networking, sharing of good practices, awards and different capacity building activities for women empowerment.</p> <p>They also develop the Matesella leadership programme for undergraduate and MA students, with the aim of fostering the presence of women in STEAM fields inside and outside academia</p>				
Link	<p>https://ejecon.org/</p> <p>https://ejecon.org/matesella/</p>				

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4.-Analysis of programmes main features

Leadership in HEIs is highly influenced by the changes performed in the last decades in HE system, which has moved from the traditional “academic and collegial management” to what Chandler calls “New Public Management”, also known as ‘New Managerialism’. However, it is commonly agreed that the specific cultural features of HEIs means difficulties in the implementation of management principles from other sectors (Chandler et al. 2002; Birnbaum 1988 ; Bergquist 1992) and point out the need to align the leadership of change to university culture (Kezar and Eckel 2002; Lueddeke 1999 ; Middlehurst 1997). Most of the initiatives identified focus the approach of these new leadership strategies on the individual level, implementing training or mentoring programmes for potential or new leaders. However, as stated by Eckel et al. (1998), in order to achieve the goals and promote institutional change, HEIs need to be both intentional and continuous. Nevertheless, most of the initiatives/programmes target the “leaders” as individuals, which according to Randall and Coakley is no longer “acceptable” (Randall & Coakley 2007:326). According to these authors, academic leadership should consider different stakeholders to achieve change (326). Thus, initiatives such as the abovementioned *U4 Academic Leadership Programme*, *Leadership Development Programme*, or *Humane* would be framed in the so called “transformational leadership” based on the motivation of leaders to excel beyond expectations (Ramsden 1988; Bass 1985; Bass and Avolio 1994). This approach is also the one adopted in most initiatives dealing with female leadership (Eagly, Johannesen-Schmidt & Van Engen, 2003).

Most of the initiatives and programs identified focus on the training and mentoring of women. The importance of these initiatives is widely supported by the literature (Ballenger, 2010; Madsen, Logman and Daniel, 2012; McCarthy 2004). The exhaustive mapping of training and capacity building developed by Madsen et al. (2012) concludes that these kind of interventions show a great potential for institutional change (Awang-Hashim et al. 2016). However, in most occasions these interventions are focused in the individual axe, targeting female leaders to enlarge their skills and values towards leadership. Undoubtedly, empowering and developing women capacities is key to promote their access to leadership positions. This individual approach is also captured in the “Leadership Continuum” developed by Morahan et al. (2011), an integrated framework to approach female advancement in academic leadership. These types of interventions and practices correspond to the approach of “equipping” women. In order to design and develop effective training and capacity building programmes, context based approach and “contextual appropriateness” plays a central role as stated by Ballenger (2010). In this regards, mentoring can play a significant role in advising women and potential future leaders on addressing ways to overcome contextual, cultural and structural barriers for female academic leadership.

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Thus, initiatives such as AdvanceHE, the GME or the APA LIWP seek women empowerment through the development of workshops and training programmes which provide participants with self-tailored experiences and skills programmes. Therefore, these programmes and initiatives build on the assumption that women lack confidence, have little negotiation skills, are risk-averse, and perpetuate the stereotype of women assuming domestic responsibilities. However, as Kramer pointed out, these is not sustained by academic evidence, and what is worse, reinforces the idea of “fixing the women”(Kramer 2019). This author highlights that the real issue lying beneath leadership in general, but also in HEIs, is the different dynamics that women and men face in the workplace.

Some of the initiatives contain also mentoring schemes. Even though these mentoring schemes also address female leaders, Ballenger et al. affirm that their aim is not at the “individual” level, but at fighting against stereotypes and structural barriers (Ballenger et al. 2010; 6). According to these authors, creating support networks and mentorship programmes help women researchers not only to identify and overcome structural barriers, but also to identify gender inequalities and discrimination. This opinion is shared by other authors, who also affirm that these kind of mentoring/coaching/sponsorship initiatives help women to reduce obstacles and bias linked to power relationships and male environment (Reiss 2015) and, even more, to recognise opportunities for career progression (Baltodano et al. 2012:74). Some of the aforementioned initiatives such as Advance HE, IDA programme, HERS programme or the initiatives developed by NTNU or Makerere Universities include mentoring schemes as a complement for the capacity building programs. Despite the fact that these mentoring activities also target female leaders, the focus is broader and do not target individual capacities of women, but try to help them in overcoming institutional and structural biases and resistances.

However, as shown by Fusch and Mrigh (2011), in order to achieve structural change, coordinated activities and overall measures are needed. To this end, networking and awareness raising activities are important to not only raise awareness among female leaders, but also to promote mutual support and role models (Saglamer 2011). Baltodano et al. also agree on the need of specific leadership programmes targeting women but highlighted that the need “more than information and training” for effective career progression and that for that purpose, the use of networking activities can be useful (Baltodano et al. 2012). Based on the European experience and the work performed by EWORA, Gulsun Saglamer states that networking events and meeting have allowed female leaders to share experiences and find common approaches to improve the situation of women in academia (Saglamer 2011). Networking is also a strong component of the Swedish IDA programme with a more national/regional approach.

Among the initiatives identified to promote female leadership we would underline the potential impact of existing practices due to their structural approach and combination of activities to achieve sustainable institutional change.

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Regarding general initiatives to promote leadership (not specific for female leadership) the Polish legal reform in the sector of education is a good example of tackling structural issues and the promotion innovative leadership.

Among the specific initiatives to promote female leadership, the dataset promoted by Academia.net is a useful tool to enlarge the list of candidates for leadership positions, helping to refute the argument commonly used by HEIs that it is difficult to find female candidates for top management positions. This dataset not only can be used to enlarge the list of potential applicants, but also gives visibility to the pool of highly qualified female candidates.

The Academic Career Map of the University of Leicester is also an inspiring practice searching for a structural reform of the University as a whole. Instead of targeting women for specific actions (even though it also includes some training activities) the career map emphasises the recognition and added value of different areas usually undertaken by women. They approach the challenges of career progression of women in a holistic way and they combine different measures and direct actions to achieve the goal of transforming institutional promotion processes.

Ballenger et al., state the relevance of affirmative action and they gather different testimonies explaining the role of these controversial actions to address structural conditions and barriers (Ballenger et al. 2010). GENIE initiative in Gothenburg and the NTNU and Agder University policies are clear examples of the added value and success of these kind of initiatives that usually face great resistances. Nevertheless, it is clear that both the regional and national context have a huge relevance for the application of this kind of measures and the transference to different countries and regions where there is less awareness on the importance of gender equality in research. But, we have also identified some structural programmes in different regional areas that share this holistic and structural approach, such as the cases of Makerere University in Uganda and HERS programme in South Africa.

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5.- Conclusions

Among the practices/programmes identified, training initiatives mean the majority of them, either as mere training or capacity building programmes or combined with other activities. Training activities are usually combined with mentoring and awareness raising activities and eventually have been included in structural programmes combined with direct support and positive actions. Capacity building activities have been applied across all regions but with particular impact in Europe and America (12 and 7 identified practices respectively).

For this report, secondary and primary sources have been used. The desk research performed has allowed us to identify initiatives all over the world addressing leadership in HEI and the survey distributed among the EURAXESS members has provided us information about programmes in place at EURAXESS partner institutions. These institutions reported 8 positive and support actions, which reveals a high consciousness about the impact of direct supporting actions for the structural change in HEI, as sustained by Ballenger et al. On the contrary, EURAXESS respondents only reported 2 training initiatives against the 22 identified in the desk analysis. This low level of awareness about training initiatives can be partially explained by the fact that although EURAXESS is present in many HEIs across Europe, it is a network very specialized on supporting international mobility of researchers. In recent times, the initiative has been engaging more in career development support but it is highly likely that a majority of the recipients of the survey still have a limited knowledge about gender equality support measures within the institution. In line with the aims of the GEARING Roles project, through this consultation and the posterior sharing of this report we expect to also contribute to raising awareness about women leadership support in HEIs among this community.

According to the analysis performed, training initiatives are commonly combined with mentoring Schemes in USA, while in other regions have been combined with direct actions and networking activities.

This evident protagonism of training and capacity building is perceived by some authors as focus on “fixing the women” built on stereotypes and with little literature support instead of addressing structural barriers for women in HEI and as an insufficient approach to the promotion of female leadership. Networking initiatives are identified by some authors as a key element not only for sharing information and knowledge, but also to showcase the role of female leaders. Even though we have only identified one programme of a joint dataset, we find this experience potentially interesting, not only because it aims at fighting one of the more common arguments used to justify the lack of women in these positions (lack of women with the required expertise) but also because it can be easily transferred to different regional contexts and institutions.

Furthermore, we would like to stress the spread of these kind of initiatives all over the world. It is true that we have found a higher amount of initiatives among European HEIs, but this can be also explained

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by the fact that EURAXESS partners are mainly from Europe. However, some of the initiatives identified in other regions such as the HERS programme in East Africa are really structural and show a great commitment of African HEIs.

Finally, it is important to highlight how the same pattern we have identified in the case of leadership in HEIs is followed in other sectors. From the assessed practices, most of them brings together a combination of training sessions for women aspiring to leadership positions (in most of the cases to top management positions, but sometimes these practices are extended to middle managers) and networking events where female leaders can share their experiences with young women as well as other leaders (both female and male. Finally, mentor schemes are developed specially at a company-level in order to accompany early-career female professionals throughout its career development.

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